

CORPORATE SYSTEM OF EDUCATIONAL AND METHODOLOGICAL SERVICES

Brytov Oleksii Senior Teacher

Artuhov Vitalii PhD, Associate Professor

Hiorhizova-Hai Viktoriia PhD, Associate Professor

Kyriusha Bogdan PhD, Associate Professor

Stikanov Valerii PhD, Associate Professor

System Design department, Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute, Kyiv, Ukraine

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In the context of a pandemic, remote work and education, there is often a need for simple and convenient remote access to corporate resources. Therefore, along with specialized distance learning systems, sending documents by e-mail, using public services for exchanging files, and creating VPN channels to program resources are widely used. The downside of this approach is the transfer of control over confidential data to a third party, the inconvenience of work due to the lack of access to all necessary resources centrally.

An alternative may be to build a private cloud system of educational and methodological services. The system was built using a technology stack that has already become standard for the implementation of complex software systems: microservice architecture, Docker containerization, Kubernetes container orchestration system. The available computing resources made it possible to build a fault-tolerant Kubernetes cluster with elements of physical and logical reservation.

A number of services in container form were described by special manifests to be launched by the orchestrator and deployed on the cluster. To store and use container images, we use our own docker registry. The built-in registry of the already used GitLab repository management system was used. Currently the system consists of a Web page for selecting services accessed via HTTPS from a browser and 4 services. The services include: Nextcloud open source software for storing and exchanging office and study materials, OnlyOffice for viewing and editing documents, and two departmental programs – for checking student program code for plagiarism and for automated scheduling of classes. The Antivirus for files plugin is included in Nextcloud containers, which allows you to check files at the download stage before they are written to the Nextcloud storage.

Service data is stored in Persistent Volumes attached to pods via NFS-Samba. The architecture provides that one volume can be connected to several containers. Backups of the corresponding databases and directories are periodically performed and stored separately.

To authorize users and differentiate their access rights to the system, integration with the departmental service of Microsoft Active Directory via the LDAP protocol has been introduced.

The introduction of such systems that allow you to provide secure centralized access to the necessary software resources, service and educational documentation, collect and check student work, will make working remotely more convenient and productive.